

KICHIK O'LCHAMLI LEYBNITS ALGEBRALARINING KVAZI-DIFFERENSIYALASHLARI VA ULARNING XOSSALARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada kichik o'lchamli Leybnits algebralarining kvazi-differensiallashtirishlari va ularning xossalari haqida olingan natijalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Leybnits algebralari, differensiallashtirish, kvazi-differensiallashtirish, umumlashgan differensiallashtirish, sentroid va kvazi-sentroidlar.*

ABSTRACT

The article presents the results obtained about quasi-differentiations of small-dimension Leibniz algebras and their properties.

Key words: *Leibniz algebras, differentiation, quasi-differentiation, generalized differentiation, centroids and quasi-centroids.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлены полученные результаты о квазидифференцировании алгебр Лейбница малой размерности и их свойствах.

Ключевые слова: *Алгебры Лейбница, дифференцирование, квазидифференцирование, обобщенное дифференцирование, центроиды и квазицентроиды.*

KIRISH

Hozirgi kunda Li algebralarning umumlashmasi hisoblangan Leybnits algebralari sinfi jadal suratda o'rganilmoqda. Ta'kidlash joizki, Leybnits ayniyatini qanoatlantiruvchi algebralarning birinchi bo'lib 1965-yilda A.Bloxning ishida D-algebralarning nomi bilan kiritilgan edi. Lekin, D-algebralarni o'rganishga unchalik e'tibor berilmagan bo'lib, faqatgina J.L. Lode va T.Pirashvilining ishlaridan keyingina Leybnits algebralari jadal suratda o'rganila boshlandi va hozirgi kunga kelib bu algebralarga bag'ishlangan bir qator maqolalar chop qilindi Leybnits algebralari o'tgan asrning 90-yillarida fransuz matematigi J.L. Lode tomonidan ushbu

$$[x, [y, z]] = [[x, y], z] - [[x, z], y]$$

Leybnits ayniyati bilan xarakterlanadigan algebra sifatida fanga kiritilgan. 1998-yildan boshlab Leybnits algebrasining strukturaviy nazariyasini Sh.A. Ayupov va B.A. Omirovlar o'rgana boshladi. Algebraning o'lchami qancha kattalashgan sari, uni tavsiflash shuncha murakkab bo'ladi. Nilpotent Leybnits algebralari bilan Ayupov Sh.A., Omirov B.A., Raximov I.S., Rixsiboev I.M., Xudoyberdiyev A.X. va boshqalar shug'ullangan. Katta o'lchamdagi nilpotent Li algebralarni ham o'rganish murakkab bo'lgani uchun, nilpotent algebralarning bir necha sinflarga bo'linadi. Masalan, nol filiform, filiform, kvazi filiform va boshqa sinflar.

So'nggi yillarda noassotsiativ algebralarning differentsiallashtirishlari va differentsiallashtirishlarning umumlashmalari hisoblangan qator operatorlar keng o'rganilmoqda. Xususan, kvazi-differentsiallashtirishlar tushunchalari operator algebralardan tashqari Li va Leybnits algebralari uchun ham o'rganildi. Ushbu maqolada kichik o'lchamli Leybnits algebralarning kvazi-differentsiallashtirishlari tushunchasi o'rganiladi. Kichik o'lchamli Leybnits algebralarning kvazi-differentsiallashtirishlari va ularning xossalari aniqlanadi.

Ta'rif 1. F maydonda berilgan $(L, [-, -])$ algebraning ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlari uchun quyidagi Leybnits ayniyati o'rinli bo'lsa:

$$[x, [y, z]] = [[x, y], z] - [[x, z], y],$$

u holda $(L, [-, -])$ algebra Leybnits algebrasi deb ataladi.

Ta’rif 2. Aytaylik, $d: L \rightarrow L$ chiziqli akslantirish bo’lsin. Agar $(L, [-, -])$ Leybnits algebrasining ixtiyoriy elementlari uchun quyidagi tenglik bajarilsa,

$$d([x, y]) = [d(x), y] + [x, d(y)],$$

u holda d chiziqli akslantirish L Leybnits algebrasining differentsiallashi deyiladi.

Barcha differentsiallashlar to‘plamini $Der(L)$ kabi belgilaymiz.

Ta’rif 3. Agar $D \in End(L)$ akslantirish uchun, $\exists D', D'' \in End(L)$ akslantirishlar topilib, $\forall x, y \in L$ elementlar uchun quyidagi ayniyat bajarilsa,

$$[D(x), y] + [x, D'(y)] = D''([x, y])$$

u holda D akslantirishga L Leybnits algebrasining **umumlashgan differentsiillashi** deyiladi.

Ta’rif 4. Agar $D \in End(L)$ akslantirish uchun, $\exists D' \in End(L)$ akslantirish topilib, $\forall x, y \in L$ elementlar uchun quyidagi ayniyat bajarilsa,

$$[D(x), y] + [x, D(y)] = D'([x, y])$$

u holda D akslantirishga L Leybnits algebrasining **kvazi-differentsiillashi** deyiladi.

L Leybnits algebrasining barcha umumlashgan va kvazi differentsiillashlari to‘plami mos ravishda $GDer(L)$ va $QDer(L)$ kabi belgilanadi. Ta’kidlash joizki, ixtiyoriy differentsiillash kvazi differentsiillash bo‘ladi. Biroq, kvazi-differentsiillashlar oddiy differentsiillash bo‘lmasligi mumkin.

Endi algebraning sentroidi, kvazi-sentoidi va sentral differentsiillashlari tushunchalarini aniqlaymiz.

Ta’rif 5. L Leybnits algebrasining $\forall x, y \in L$ elementlari uchun quyidagi,

$$[D(x), y] = [x, D(y)] = D([x, y])$$

ayniyatni bajaradigan $D \in End(L)$ akslantirishlarga L Leybnits algebrasining **sentroidi** deyiladi. Barcha sentroidlar to‘plamini $C(L)$ bilan belgilanadi.

Ta’rif 6. L Leybnits algebrasining $\forall x, y \in L$ elementlari uchun quyidagi,

$$[D(x), y] = [x, D(y)]$$

ayniyatni bajaradigan $D \in End(L)$ akslantirishlarga L Leybnits algebrasining **kvazi-sentroidi** deyiladi. Barcha kvazi-sentroidlar to‘plamini $QC(L)$ bilan belgilanadi.

Ta’rif 7. L Leybnits algebrasining $\forall x, y \in L$ elementlari uchun quyidagi,

$$[D(x), y] = [x, D(y)] = D([x, y]) = 0$$

ayniyatni bajaradigan $D \in \text{End}(L)$ akslantirishlarga L Leybnits algebrasining **sentral differensiallashi** deyiladi. Barcha sentral differensiallashlar to‘plamini $Z\text{Der}(L)$ bilan belgilanadi. Ma‘lumki,

$$Z\text{Der}(L) \subseteq \text{Der}(L) \subseteq Q\text{Der}(L) \subseteq G\text{Der}(L) \subseteq \text{End}(L)$$

munosabat o‘rinli bo‘ladi. Shuningdek,

$$C(L) \subseteq QC(L) \subseteq Q\text{Der}(L)$$

munosabat ham o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Ikki o‘lchamli Leybnits algebralarining kvazi-differensiallashlari:

Ma‘lumki, har qanday ikki-o‘lchamli Leybnits algebrasi quyidagi izomorf bo‘lmagan Leibnits algebralaridan biriga izomorf:

$$L_1: [e_1, e_1] = e_2$$

$$L_2: [e_1, e_2] = -[e_2, e_1] = e_2$$

$$L_3: [e_1, e_2] = [e_2, e_2] = e_1$$

NATIJARAR:

Biz shu uch xil 2-o‘lchamli algebralarining barcha differensiallashlari, kvazi-differensiallashlari, sentroidi, kvazi-sentroidi va umumlashgan differensiallashlarini umumiy ko‘rinishlarini aniqlaymiz:

Teorema 1. $L_1: [e_1, e_1] = e_2$ algebraning differensiallashlari quyidagicha ko‘rinishga ega:

$L_1: [e_1, e_1] = e_2$				
$\text{Der}(L_1)$	$Q\text{Der}(L_1)$	$G\text{Der}(L_1)$	$C(L_1)$	$QC(L_1)$
$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ 0 & 2d_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ 0 & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ 0 & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ 0 & d_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ 0 & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$

Teorema 2. $L_2: [e_1, e_2] = -[e_2, e_1] = e_2$ algebraning differensiallashlari quyidagicha ko‘rinishga ega:

$$L_2: [e_1, e_2] = -[e_2, e_1] = e_2$$

$Der(L_2)$	$QDer(L_2)$	$GDer(L_2)$	$C(L_2)$	$QC(L_2)$
$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ 0 & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$

Teorema 3. $L_3: [e_1, e_2] = [e_2, e_2] = e_1$ algebraning differensiallashlari quyidagicha ko‘rinishga ega:

$L_3: [e_1, e_2] = [e_2, e_2] = e_1$				
$Der(L_3)$	$QDer(L_3)$	$GDer(L_3)$	$C(L_3)$	$QC(L_3)$
$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & 0 \\ d_{11} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{21} + d_{22} & 0 \\ d_{21} & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$

Uch o‘lchamli nilpotent Leybnits algebralarining kvazi-differensiallashlari:

Bizga quyidagi uch o‘lchamli nilpotent Leybnits algebralari berilgan bo‘lsin:

λ_1 : *abelian*;

λ_2 : $[e_1, e_1] = e_2$;

λ_3 : $[e_2, e_3] = e_1, [e_3, e_2] = -e_1$;

λ_4 : $[e_2, e_1] = e_3, [e_1, e_2] = \alpha e_3, \alpha \neq \alpha^{-1} (\alpha \in C)$;

λ_5 : $[e_1, e_1] = e_3, [e_2, e_1] = e_3, [e_1, e_2] = -e_3$

λ_6 : $[e_1, e_1] = e_2, [e_2, e_1] = e_3$.

Bu algebralar uchun kvazi-differensiallashlar to‘plamini topamiz.

Tasdiq 1. λ_1 : *abelian* algebraning barcha differensiallashlari fazosi matritsasining umumiy ko‘rinishi quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ \gamma_1 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Teorema 4. $\lambda_2: [e_1, e_1] = e_2$ algebralar uchun kvazi-differensiallashlar fazosi matritsasining umumiy ko‘rinishi quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

$$QDer(\lambda_2) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

λ_2 algebraning qolgan differensiallashlarini isbotsiz quyidagi jadvalda keltiramiz:

$\lambda_2: [e_1, e_1] = e_2$			
$Der(\lambda_2)$	$GDer(\lambda_2)$	$C(\lambda_2)$	$QC(\lambda_2)$
$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & 2\alpha_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$

Teorema 5. $\lambda_3: [e_2, e_3] = e_1, [e_3, e_2] = -e_1$ algebralar uchun kvazi-differensiallashlar fazosining matritsasi quyidagi ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi:

$$QDer(\lambda_3) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ \gamma_1 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$\lambda_3: [e_2, e_3] = e_1, [e_3, e_2] = -e_1$			
$Der(\lambda_3)$	$GDer(\lambda_3)$	$C(\lambda_3)$	$QC(\lambda_3)$
$\begin{pmatrix} \beta_2 + \gamma_3 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ \gamma_1 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ \gamma_1 & \gamma_2 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_1 & \alpha_1 & 0 \\ \gamma_1 & 0 & \alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & 0 \\ \gamma_1 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$

Teorema 6. $\lambda_4: [e_2, e_1] = e_3, [e_1, e_2] = \alpha e_3, \alpha \neq \alpha^{-1}, (\alpha \in C)$ algebralar uchun kvazi-differensiallashlar fazosining matritsasi quyidagi ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi:

$$QDer(\lambda_4) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$\lambda_4: [e_2, e_1] = e_3, [e_1, e_2] = \alpha e_3, \alpha \neq \alpha^{-1}, (\alpha \in C)$			
$Der(\lambda_4)$	$GDer(\lambda_4)$	$C(\lambda_4)$	$QC(\lambda_4)$
$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 + \beta_2 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$

Teorema 7. $\lambda_5: [e_1, e_1] = e_3, [e_2, e_1] = e_3, [e_1, e_2] = -e_3$ algebra uchun kvazi-differensiallashlar fazosining matritsasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$QDer(\lambda_5) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$\lambda_5: [e_1, e_1] = e_3, [e_2, e_1] = e_3, [e_1, e_2] = -e_3$			
$Der(\lambda_5)$	$GDer(\lambda_5)$	$C(\lambda_5)$	$QC(\lambda_5)$
$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2\alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$

Teorema 8. $\lambda_6: [e_1, e_1] = e_2, [e_2, e_1] = e_3$ algebra uchun kvazi-differensiallashlar fazosining matritsasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$QDer(\lambda_6) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$\lambda_6: [e_1, e_1] = e_2, [e_2, e_1] = e_3$			
$Der(\lambda_6)$	$GDer(\lambda_6)$	$C(\lambda_6)$	$QC(\lambda_6)$
$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & 2\alpha_1 & \alpha_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 3\alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & \alpha_1 & \beta_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$

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